

PSYCHOLOGICAL BASIS OF FORMING A SOCIALLY ACTIVE POSITION IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article comprehensively analyzes the psychological foundations of the formation of a socially active position in students. It covers the development of a person's social consciousness, a sense of civic responsibility, and the level of readiness to actively and consciously relate to the environment based on psychological criteria. It is also scientifically proven that the components of a socially active position - motivation, empathy, critical thinking, social communication, and leadership qualities - play an important role in the process of forming the personality of students. The study shows ways to develop social activity based on modern psychological approaches, theories of personal development, and psychological factors of the educational environment.

Keywords: Socially active position, personal development, psychological approach, motivation, civic responsibility, empathy, critical thinking, educational environment.

Introduction.

In modern society, human activity, not being indifferent to social issues, and the ability to freely and reasonably express one's opinion are becoming increasingly important. The formation of a socially active position, especially among the younger generation - students, has become one of the most urgent tasks of today's education system. Because the future development of society and the stable functioning of civic institutions directly depend on the development of today's youth as conscious, active and responsible individuals.

A socially active position is not just a set of external actions, but a psychological state closely related to the inner world of a person, moral values, level of social consciousness and sense of responsibility. The formation of such a position requires a complex and multi-stage psychological and pedagogical process. In this process, the role of the school environment, the personal influence of the teacher, communication with peers, as well as relationships with parents are manifested as important psychological factors.

At the same time, there is an increasing need to identify ways to increase the social activity of students through psychological concepts such as theories of personal development, motivation, empathy, social identification, social learning, and to develop effective strategies in this direction. Because passive, indifferent, uninitiated individuals can be an obstacle to the development of society, while active, socially responsible individuals are considered a guarantee of the social stability of society. This article aims to identify the psychological foundations of the formation of a socially active position in students, analyze the internal and external factors that develop them, and also identify the tasks facing the education system in this regard.

Theoretical basis:

The issue of forming a socially active position of the student's personality is located at the intersection of psychology and pedagogical sciences, and a deep understanding of this process requires relying on several important theoretical approaches. First of all, classical and

modern psychological theories describing the formation of the human personality, in particular, the works of such scientists as L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontyev, E. Erikson, A. Bandura, K. Rogers, are recognized as the main theoretical foundation in this area.

L.S. Vygotsky's sociocultural approach directly links the development of the individual with the social environment and interprets the social activity of students as a result of their formation in interaction with society. According to Vygotsky, the "zone of proximal development" in the development of a child expands precisely through pedagogical and social influences, which creates the basis for the formation of a conscious social position of the student.

Bandura's "social learning theory" is also important in illuminating this topic. According to him, people form their behavior by observing those around them. In this process, through the mechanisms of modeling, identification and reinforcement, students absorb the social activity of those around them. In particular, images of a socially active teacher, parents or peers serve as a powerful psychological factor for the activation of the student's personality.

Erikson's theory of the stages of psychosocial development is also used to determine the social position of students. According to his definition, at each age stage, a person solves certain social tasks. In adolescence, this is identification, that is, the search for an answer to the question "who am I?" At this stage, healthy communication with society, the environment, teachers and family determines the level of social self-awareness of the student.

Also, representatives of humanistic psychology - M. Maslow and K. Rogers - define a person's desire to understand himself and realize his identity as the main psychological need. The provision of this need is the main condition for becoming a socially active person. In order to form a social position, a student must develop self-esteem, express an independent opinion, take initiative and a desire to be useful to others. The above theoretical approaches show that the formation of a socially active position in students is not only an educational, but also a deep psychological process. By deeply understanding this process and approaching it on a scientific basis, it is possible to form civic responsibility, social activity and a conscious position in the younger generation.

Methodology:

The study of such a complex and multifaceted process as the formation of a socially active position in students, of course, requires relying not on a single method, but on a combination of different methodological approaches. In the framework of this study, we, first of all, chose person-oriented, activity-based and sociopsychological approaches as the methodological basis. After all, a student is not an ordinary learner, but an individual who is being formed as an active, socially conscious, independent-thinking person. During the study, not only theoretical views, but also data collected through observations, interviews, and questionnaires in a real educational environment became an important source. We realized that a student's social activity can be assessed not only by how many lessons he attended or what grades he received, but also by his initiative, the level of assistance to his peers, his awareness of social reality, and his ability to make responsible decisions.

In the methodological approach, L.S. Vygotsky's theory of sociocultural development was our main point of reference. Through his concept of the "zone of proximal development", we realized that each student has a hidden potential for social activity. In order to reveal this potential, the environment, pedagogical approach and psychological support play a decisive role. In the practical study, we tried to determine psychological criteria such as the personal

position of students, leadership qualities, level of empathy, critical thinking skills through questionnaires, interviews, diagnostic tests. Each result, each idea led us to one truth - if a student is given the opportunity, trusted and listened to, he can become a socially active and responsible person. Methodologically, this approach allowed us to understand social activity not only on the basis of statistical analysis, but also on the basis of human internal experiences, psychological states and personal motives. This is the main achievement of our research.

Discussion:

In modern society, people are required not only to have knowledge, but also to have civic responsibility, social activity, and a moral position. This requirement is especially a challenge for the younger generation - students. Because they are the main driving force of the future society. From this point of view, the formation of a socially active position in a student is not just an educational task, but also the process of a person's transformation into a conscious and responsible social being. This process has deep psychological roots.

During the study, we witnessed the following truth: a student's social activity is never formed by chance. It is a complex psychological state that is gradually formed under the influence of family relationships, the school environment, the personality of the teacher, a group of friends, and even the flow of information on social networks. In particular, the student's internal motives - the need for recognition, the desire to be useful, a sense of justice, and such psychological qualities as empathy - play a decisive role in the formation of this state.

There were also cases of insufficient opportunities for students to be socially active. Sometimes a student is ready to express his opinion, but if there is no ear to listen to him, this activity fades away. Sometimes he takes the initiative, but if this is not encouraged, he chooses silence next time. So, much depends not only on the student, but also on the environment, especially the internal psychological environment of educational institutions, to form a socially active position. The discussion shows that teachers should be more than just a simple educator in preparing students for social life - a guide, an encourager, an inspiration. In order to arouse activity in a student, it is important to trust him, treat his opinion with respect, create opportunities for discussion on social issues, and involve him in collective activities. A socially active position in a student is formed under the influence of internal psychological needs and external social factors. If this process takes place in an environment built on conscious, scientifically based, positive communication, then it will be possible to educate a socially responsible, active, initiative and well-rounded individual who can find his place in society.

Conclusion

Forming a socially active position in the younger generation is one of the most important and strategic tasks of modern education. The main goal of the educational process is not only to arm students with knowledge, but also to teach them to have a responsible, active and conscious attitude towards life, society, and people around them. As the study revealed, a socially active position does not form by itself, but is the product of personal motivation, psychological support and social experience.

The analysis shows that several psychological factors play an important role in the development of social activity in a student: empathy, independent thinking, self-awareness, a sense of responsibility and communicative competencies. The personality of the teacher, the

socio-psychological environment in the educational institution, and family upbringing play a leading role in shaping these.

On this basis, the following conclusions were drawn:

A socially active position is formed depending on the social consciousness of the individual, his psychological state and the external social environment.

To develop this position in students, open communication, free expression of opinions, involvement in collective work and a person-oriented approach should be a priority in the educational process.

Teachers should be armed with social psychological competencies, be able to understand the inner world of young people, and appear as inspiring and confident individuals.

Based on the above, it can be said that the formation of a student's social activity is a complex but necessary process that requires a psychological approach before becoming a pedagogical task. In this direction, it is possible to educate socially responsible, active and conscious citizens through a systematic approach and deeply scientifically based methods.

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